

TECHNOLOGIES TO ENRICH THE VOCABULARY OF STUDENTS WITH MENTAL DISABILITY

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Abstract: In this article, there are scientific and practical opinions about the activities and technologies used to increase the vocabulary of students with mental retardation.

Key words: Educational system, technology, speech skills, vocabulary, L.S. Vygotsky, "Mahbub ul-qulun", Alisher Navoi.

In terms of content modernization of the continuing education system and raising the educational efficiency to a new level of quality, when it comes to the public education system, first of all, the official that provides its legal and regulatory basis it is necessary to refer to the documents. The state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan towards the disabled was established in 1991 by the Law "On Social Protection of the Disabled in the Republic of Uzbekistan". This law provides measures to protect the rights and interests of this group of people in order to create opportunities and conditions that will help them live a full life on an equal basis with other citizens, actively participate in the economic and political life of society, and fulfill their civic obligations. envisages a system. This law was adopted shortly after the independence of our Republic, and in general, it regulates the relations between the state and social societies mobilized to protect the health of the population, prevent disability and create conditions for the integration of disabled people into society. It is considered to be one of the first serious legal documents.

This period of students is the most effective and rapid process of child development. Therefore, identifying and studying the abilities of students with mental retardation and carrying out psychological-pedagogical correction work with them in necessary cases, enriching their vocabulary as early as possible, will further realize the effectiveness of this pedagogical-corrective work. This is based on the fact that children with organic deficiency need to develop their mental activity more actively than their healthy peers. Speech and vocabulary are the most important in a child's development. The formation of a person, as well as all mental processes, is closely related to the development of speech.

In the works created by great geniuses such as Yusuf Khos Hajib, Imam al-Bukhari, Abu Nasir Farabi, At-Tirmizi, Alisher Nawai, speech and its importance in human activity are expressed in vivid examples. Yusuf Khos Hajib, in his encyclopedic work "Kutadgu Bilig", which embodies the guidelines of manners, education and spiritual maturity, considers language to be the main key to acquiring knowledge and intelligence¹. According to Alloma, a person polishes his knowledge, intellect, intelligence and expresses his thoughts thanks to language.

¹ Yusuf Xos Hojib. Qutadg'u bilig. Text and description in modern Uzbek language. – Tashkent: Fan, 1971;

Language and speech increase a person's dignity and reach greatness. However, you should think about the words, know them, and speak only when the time comes. Only then will the language and words be very useful. If you speak without thinking, its effectiveness decreases, as a result, a person lowers his value. Therefore, a logical effect is achieved by speaking a little, but in words.

Abu Nasr Farabi says about the importance of lexicology, grammar and logic in correct speech, making correct logical conclusions, meaningful and beautiful speech: "How to teach and receive education, when we come to (the problem of) how to express, explain, how to ask and how to answer, I affirm that the first knowledge about this is the science of language that gives names to objects and events..."².

Language vocabulary and speech are dialectically related social-historical, social-psychological phenomena, and language exists as a communication tool, and speech as a communication method. Vocabulary cannot be separated from speech, and speech cannot be separated from thought. No matter what language a person speaks, he expresses his thoughts with words, because they have mutual harmony. A. Navoi considers language to be the only distinguishing feature between man and animal.

Speech disorders are deviations from the norms of the language due to the weakening of the psychophysiological mechanisms of the speaking person, which are accepted in a certain language environment and work normally. From the point of view of communicative theory, speech disorders are disorders of the cognitive process and means of communication. Therefore, the duty and task of any cultural society is to provide qualified assistance to members of the society with speech defects in a timely manner.

Mentally retarded children develop their speech later and have a number of deficiencies compared to their peers whose vocabulary is developing normally. Pronunciation defects in violation of the analysis and synthesis of the sound of the word, poverty of the vocabulary, lack of formation of the grammatical structure have a negative effect on the development of the speech and thinking of the mentally retarded child. Even if some independent sentences appear, children's communication is characterized by a number of phonetic and grammatical disorders. In particular, the onset of interpersonal relationships is delayed due to impaired speech. Disruption of speech in mentally retarded children is determined by high nervous activity and the specificity of its mental formation.

According to S. Ya. Rubinstein, the main reasons for the incomplete development of speech vocabulary in mentally retarded children are the slow development of new differential connections in the brain and the weakness of functional layers in all analyzers³.

Scientists who have applied the features of development of the speech vocabulary of mentally retarded children show that they have a pathological interactivity and a very weak interest in the environment. Therefore, in organizing the education of children belonging to this

² "The city of noble people" Abu Nasr Farabiy - Tashkent / "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House – 2004y. – 42p.

³ S.Ya. Rubinshtein // Defectology.- 1990.- No. 3.- P. 95.

category, it is necessary to use methods of influence aimed at activating their cognitive activity and developing their speech. Didactic games are very important in this. In the scientific and special literature, we witnessed the need to improve the ways of its development in the study of the speech of mentally retarded children of preschool age. The importance of using didactic games in the development of the speech of mentally retarded children is great. Because the importance of the game, which is the main activity of children, becomes more important in raising children in general educational institutions.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND REVIEW.

A number of scientists have conducted effective scientific research on the development of the vocabulary of students with mental retardation (L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Gvozdev, D.B. Elkonin, A.P. Sokolov, N.Kh. Shvachkin, A. Vallon and others).

Well-known scientists S. Ya. Rubinshtein, G. A. Kashe, V. G. Petrova, J. I. Shif, V. I. Lubovsky noted that the lack of development of vocabulary in mentally retarded children lags behind to a certain extent.

In the structure of mental retardation, the lack of development of vocabulary in speech is observed. The speech of mentally retarded children has its own characteristics, and it is effective to develop it at school if:

- in the process of developing the speech of children with mental retardation, when using game activities, the current situation and personal characteristics of the intellectual problems of each pupil are taken into account and the principle of individual orientation is observed;
- effective use of game technologies that are the basis for improving the correctional-developmental system based on the speech and mental development of this category of children will ensure the effectiveness of the speech development system of mentally retarded children.

Before talking about mentally retarded children, let's remember the vocabulary development processes of normally developing children. Speech development begins early in a normally developing child. In the process of learning, phonemic hearing develops, the articulatory apparatus develops. Passive vocabulary accumulates in communication with adults.

The specific aspects of the vocabulary of a mentally retarded student have attracted the attention of many authors. They recognized that disturbances in the activity of perception leave their mark in the formation of passive and active vocabularies.

Children with mental retardation have poor vocabulary, incorrect use of words, preference of passive vocabulary over active vocabulary, and difficulties in using words according to the content. These are the important reasons for the poor vocabulary in children, their low intellectual development, limited understanding and imagination about the world around them, weak verbal memory, low demand for social and speech communication, lack of interest formation⁴.

⁴ Lyublinskaya A. A. Essays on psychological development - Ed. 4th, revised, M. : "Enlightenment", 1985.- 356s.

The passive vocabulary of mentally retarded children is more than the active vocabulary, but even then a guiding question is required to repeat a word and pronounce it. On the one hand, the difficulties arise from inhibition in the cerebral cortex of mentally retarded children, and on the other hand, from peculiarities in the formation of semantic fields.

The study of A.R. Luria and O.S. Vinogradova (1978) on semantic fields showed that they are not fully formed. As a rule, the choice of words is made based on their meaning, i.e. based on meaningful similarities (high-low, apple-pear). And in children with mental retardation, the choice of words is made based on approximate, sometimes sound similarities, which once again indicates the incomplete formation of lexical systematics. Many words do not translate into concepts⁵.

The analysis of observations made with mentally retarded children shows that they have difficulties and errors in understanding the meaning of words denoting objects and situations, they cannot even point to an object that is rare in their life experience. The weight of their passive vocabulary is higher than that of active speech. Children of this category can show the images in the picture, but they do not have the mental ability to name them. Lack of active vocabulary makes it difficult for mentally retarded children to communicate with others. Mentally retarded children say some words based on the image in the picture, but do not understand the meaning of these words in other conditions and situations.

At the same time, due to the poor vocabulary, children use only one group of words, which causes the speech to be one-sided and unclear. Many authors have studied the peculiarities of the grammatical structure of speech of students with mental retardation (V.G. Petrov, M.F. Gnezdilov, M.F. Feodanov, A.P. Fedchenko, etc.). Unfortunately, we witnessed that the grammatical side of the speech of mentally retarded children of preschool age is not fully studied.

All the researchers involved in the study of speech development of mentally retarded children show that there are more speech defects in mentally retarded than in their peers whose intelligence is preserved and they say that one of the effective ways to correct and eliminate them is didactic games. those who kid. In the game, especially through the didactic game, children acquire new knowledge, concepts, skills and abilities, their speech is formed and developed. All this made it necessary for us to research the ways of using didactic games in the process of speech development in mentally retarded children.

⁵ Vinogradova A.D., Lipetskaya E.I., Matasov Yu.T., Ushakova I.P. Workshop on the psychology of a mentally retarded child. - M.: "Enlightenment", 1985.

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